

Automating Urban Cartography: A reproducible method for Agent-Based Simulation with QGIS and GAMA

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Abstract

Agent-based simulations model complex systems through the interaction of entities in an environment, where an accurate representation of that environment is crucial to reflecting reality.

This work presents a methodology for constructing two functional graphs—one for the road network and one for the pedestrian network—using data obtained from **Open Street Map**, processed and edited in **QGIS** and implemented in **GAMA**. Proper structuring of these graphs ensures realistic vehicle and pedestrian mobility, guarantees model scalability, and prevents unnecessary overhead. In addition, this approach aims to reduce manual intervention in the mapping process, facilitating the reproducibility of the model in different cities and urban contexts.

1 Introduction

Agent-based simulations allow us to model complex systems where multiple entities interact within a defined environment. In order for the simulation to faithfully reflect reality, it is essential to have an accurate representation of the space in which the agents operate. In this context, the use of geographic information systems (GIS) is key, as it enables the integration of detailed geographic information into the model.

GAMA is a simulation platform designed to facilitate the incorporation of GIS data into agent-based models. Its ability to handle different geospatial formats, convert geographic entities into agents, and provide advanced spatial analysis tools makes it a powerful tool for simulating realistic environments. However, to take full advantage of these capabilities, a structured process is necessary to correctly map a region within the simulation environment.

This document describes the essential steps to map a region in GAMA, from gathering and preparing GIS data to integrating it into the simulation. Key aspects will be addressed, such as the selection of data sources, the filtering of irrelevant information, the creation of roads, nodes, and sidewalks, building a graph of the road network, and assigning properties to spatial agents.

This manual is the result of extensive research, combined with practical testing and iterative adjustments, designed to offer a clear, simple, and scalable approach to mapping any city in the context of agent simulations. The goal is to provide a detailed, practical guide that facilitates the accurate representation of complex urban environments, reducing technical barriers and minimizing the need for manual mapping during the process, ensuring that it is reproducible and adaptable to various cities and contexts.

2 Tools used

For building the urban cartography in the agent-based simulation, several tools were used to collect, process, and model geospatial data.

2.1 QGIS

QGIS is an open-source geographic information system (GIS) that allows the visualization, editing, and analysis of geospatial data. Its compatibility with multiple formats and the availability of extensions make it a key tool for preparing cartographic data used in agent-based simulations [1].

2.2 OpenStreetMap (OSM)

OpenStreetMap is a collaborative geospatial database that provides detailed information on urban infrastructure, including roads, buildings, and points of interest. It is a collaborative and open-source project, conceived to offer free and unrestricted access to cartographic information, in contrast to proprietary platforms that impose usage limitations on their data [2]. You can access the platform at the following link: [OpenStreetMap](#).

The data obtained from OSM can be processed in QGIS and used in GAMA to represent the urban environment accurately.

2.3 GAMA

GAMA (GIS Agent-based Modeling Architecture) is a simulation platform designed for agent-based modeling of complex systems and to study their evolution over time. Its ability to handle large volumes of geospatial data and its flexibility in defining agent behaviors make it an ideal tool for simulating urban dynamics [3].

3 Initial steps to map a Region in QGIS

To represent a region in an agent-based simulation in GAMA, a series of steps is required to ensure the correct integration of geospatial data into the model. Below is a description of each of these stages. Our first objective will be to create a road graph that simulation agents representing cars can travel on.

3.1 GIS data collection with OSM

The first step in mapping a region is to obtain the appropriate geographic data. To download OSM maps directly, we will use a QGIS plugin called QuickOSM, which is integrated into QGIS.

Its symbol is:

To download and install QuickOSM in QGIS, follow these steps: Access the plugin manager. In the main menu, select **Plugins - Manage and Install Plugins**. Search for QuickOSM. Once QuickOSM appears in the search results, select it and click on the **Install Plugin** button. QuickOSM will now be available in the **Plugins** menu.

Once installed, we can consult the OSM wiki [OpenStreetMap Wiki](#), which contains detailed documentation on the different keys and values that exist. These keys represent categories of information (such as roads, buildings, parks, or points of interest), while the values specify the specific attributes within each category (for example, a road can be **residential**, **primary**, or **highway**).

3.2 Download the roads

To download all roads without filtering by type, you simply use the key **highway**. However, the main advantage of OpenStreetMap is precisely to leverage the fact that spatial data is tagged and can be filtered according to their properties. Also, if we download all the data tagged with **highway**, it will include pedestrian streets or bike lanes, whereas our goal is specifically to build a graph that only accommodates vehicle traffic. To address this, we can select exactly which types of roads interest us.

Regarding the location, we can choose to download a specific place, the area within a boundary we define manually, or its surroundings.

Figure 1: Configuration window for downloading roads by type.

Each of these queries will by default download several layers with different geometry types (polygons, lines, or points). In this case, we can delete the polygon layer since for our process of building the graph, we only need the point layer and the line layer.

The OSM database not only stores the location of roads but also relevant information such as road type, speed limits, and the number of lanes, among other useful properties.

Figure 2: Map of the city of Leganés, downloaded with the configuration provided in Figure 1. Highways (tagged *motorway*) are visible in green, while other roads (tagged *highway*) are shown in brown.

3.3 Add adjacent areas

As shown in the figure above, the graph is incomplete because it has isolated structures and is not fully accessible. This happens because, when downloading the map using “Leganés” as the boundary, the data is trimmed exactly at the edges of that area, creating cuts in the roads and interrupting connections.

Next, we download the maps of neighboring cities, such as Alcorcón, Fuenlabrada, Carabanchel, or Getafe, and edit each layer to delete any elements that do not help complete the map of Leganés with its surroundings.

To do this, enable editing mode , or simply press the Delete key.

Then we use the “Merge Vector Layers” tool to merge all these layers from different cities into one single layer, representing in this case the map of Leganés and its surroundings.

3.4 Resulting layers

As a result of the above process, we will obtain one layer with the roads and another with OSM points of interest for the desired city and, if we wish, also for the surrounding area. In the case of Leganés, the result is shown in Figure 3.

4 Create the roads

If we were to export the map of roads at this moment, it would not work in an agent-based simulation because programs like GAMA require graphs, and graphs must have edges and nodes. We will explain later how to create these nodes, and we will edit the roads again so that everything functions like a network.

4.1 Field calculator

As mentioned, one of the great advantages of OSM is that, in addition to geographic data, it also provides numerous additional attributes. To visualize these attributes, select the desired layer and click “Open Attribute Table.” This way, you can examine the various fields along with their values.

If we open the attribute table of the roads layer we have created, we can modify its values with

the field calculator. The field calculator is identified by the following icon: Make sure you are in editing mode (pencil icon). To fill in the missing values in the `maxspeed` field, we do so based on the type of road it is. For example, highways with no specified maximum speed will be given a default value of 120. We update the existing `maxspeed` field with the following code, which assigns a default value to `maxspeed` according to the type of road when not defined:

```
CASE
  WHEN "maxspeed" IS NULL THEN
    CASE
      WHEN "highway" IN ('motorway', 'motorway_link') THEN 120
      WHEN "highway" IN ('trunk', 'trunk_link') THEN 100
      WHEN "highway" IN ('primary') THEN 90
      WHEN "highway" IN ('secondary', 'secondary_link') THEN 90
      WHEN "highway" IN ('tertiary', 'tertiary_link') THEN 90
      WHEN "highway" IN ('residential') THEN 30
      ELSE NULL
    END
  ELSE "maxspeed"
END
```

We can also define a similar statement to fill in values for the field that indicates the number of lanes when it is not defined:

```
CASE
  WHEN "lanes" IS NULL THEN
    CASE
      WHEN "highway" IN ('motorway', 'motorway_link') THEN 4
      WHEN "highway" IN ('trunk', 'trunk_link') THEN 3
      WHEN "highway" IN ('primary') THEN 2
      WHEN "highway" IN ('secondary', 'secondary_link') THEN 2
      WHEN "highway" IN ('tertiary', 'tertiary_link') THEN 2
      WHEN "highway" IN ('residential') THEN 1
      ELSE 1
    END
  ELSE "lanes"
END
```

Although the table contains multiple fields, we will keep only those relevant to the simulation: `highway` (road type), `maxspeed` (maximum speed), and `lanes` (number of lanes). Other fields can be easily deleted, which simplifies the data and optimizes handling in the model.

4.2 Exportation

In the figure below, we can see the resulting map of Leganés.

Figure 3: Map of the city of Leganés, complete with its surroundings.

To export a layer in QGIS, follow these steps:

1. Right-click on the desired layer.
2. Select **Export** and then **Save Features As**.
3. Specify the fields to export and the destination path.
4. Confirm the export.

Each of the lines in the layer has an associated direction, which you can visualize in QGIS as follows:

1. Click on the layer and select **Properties**.
2. Go to the **Symbology** tab.
3. In the line configuration, select **Simple line** and change it to **Arrow**.

5 Creation of nodes

5.1 Cleaning of irrelevant information points

When downloading elements tagged as "highway" in QGIS, additional points with extra information are also included in a separate layer. To optimize the data, we will remove any elements that do not belong to the following categories:

- Bus stops (*bus stop*)
- Crosswalks (*crossing*)
- Yield signs (*give way*)
- Stop signs (*stop*)
- Traffic lights (*traffic signal*)

To filter these elements in QGIS, follow these steps:

1. Right-click on the layer and select **Filter**.
2. In the query builder, specify the criteria to include only the elements mentioned:

```
"highway" = 'bus_stop' OR  
"highway" = 'crossing' OR  
"highway" = 'give_way' OR  
"highway" = 'traffic_signals'
```

3. Apply the filter to keep only the relevant nodes.

This process cleans the information by retaining only the elements necessary for building the map.

5.2 Filtering of road nodes

After cleaning the node layer or downloading a specific subset of roads, some nodes may be irrelevant to graph construction. The presence of these unnecessary nodes can increase resource usage and affect performance.

To avoid this, we must select only those nodes located directly on the roads and relevant to the modeled scenario. This means excluding those close to but not actually on the roads, as they do not contribute useful information to the graph.

The steps are as follows:

1. **Select all nodes:** Go to the QGIS layer panel and make sure all nodes are selected.
2. **Apply the "Select by Location" tool:** Access the **Select by Location** tool, identifiable by the icon:

Configure the tool to select only nodes that intersect or are directly near the roads.

3. **Filter and apply selection:** Run the tool so that the relevant nodes remain selected.

In the tool's configuration window, ensure you properly define the parameters for intersection between nodes and roads.

Figure 4: Configuration window parameters for “Select by Location.”

This way, we select those nodes that, with respect to the roads layer, intersect, touch, or overlap with any of them.

Figure 5: Result of “Select by Location.”

In the figure above, the green points are not relevant to our next steps, as they are not on the roads. However, the yellow points do meet the criteria, being located on the roads and thus will be useful for building the graph.

Some nodes that are not directly on the roads might still be useful, such as bus stops, if you decide to include them in the project. In that case, you only need to isolate those that interest you in a new layer and later use the “Merge Vector Layers” tool.

5.3 Exportation

Next, export the selected nodes from the layer following the steps used to export the roads layer. Regarding nomenclature, this project uses the term “crossroads” to refer to all map nodes, whether or not they are actual road intersections. However, each user can choose whichever name they find most appropriate to keep their project organized.

Currently, the exported layers will be saved to disk, ensuring they are preserved. However, the layer before export is a temporary scratch layer, meaning it is stored in memory and will be lost when the computer is turned off. For this reason, it is highly recommended to save all layers you wish to keep, assigning each a descriptive name, such as **roads**, **crossroads**, etc. Redundant or unused layers should also be removed to maintain an organized project and avoid confusion.

5.4 Generation of nodes at intersections

Despite previous processing, the network is still not fully functional because some edges overlap at intersections, making it impossible to properly distinguish between different roads or select alternate routes. Figure 6 shows an example where only one of the lines has been selected, highlighting this issue. Additionally, the absence of nodes at crossing points means the system does not recognize intersections, making it impossible to define the correct connections between roads and limiting movement within the graph.

Figure 6: A single line selected in QGIS (red) with road points (purple).

To solve this problem, new nodes must be generated at the intersection points of the lines. This is done using the **Line Intersection** tool, with both the input and intersection layers being the road network. This identifies and extracts intersections within the same layer.

However, QGIS can fail during this process. To prevent interruptions, it is recommended to activate the **Ignore errors** option in the *Algorithm Settings*. Nonetheless, this option may affect the final quality of the results.

When two lines cross, the algorithm creates a node at the intersection, as expected. However, multiple points can be generated at the same crossing, since the algorithm treats each intersection between pairs of lines as a separate event. This creates an excess of nodes, and consequently a graph with more edges than necessary, affecting proper functionality.

To fix this redundancy, it is essential to delete duplicate points and keep only a single node per intersection. You can achieve this by using the **Delete Duplicate Geometries** tool in the **Vector General** menu.

5.5 Labeling of nodes

To differentiate intersections from other points of information when we merge the layers, we will use the field calculator to modify the **highway** label. We will not modify the point-of-information layer downloaded from OSM, because its **highway** field already includes relevant data such as crosswalks or traffic lights.

Instead, we will edit the intersection layer we just created, assigning it the value '**crossroad**' in the **highway** field to identify them correctly. To do this, open the attribute table, access the field calculator, and by selecting to update the **highway** field, enter the expression '**crossroad**' (in single quotes so as not to reference another field).

5.6 Adding additional points of interest

The next step is to identify and add relevant points of interest to the simulation. An example is bus stops (*bus stops*), which can be downloaded directly from OpenStreetMap (OSM). Depending on the purpose of the simulation, points of interest may vary. In our case, we focus on electric vehicle charging stations (charging points) in the city.

To obtain this information, we use the platform [Electromaps](#), which locates charging stations in various cities. Specifically, we can consult the charging points available in Leganés via the following link: [Charging Stations in Leganés](#).

To extract this data efficiently and without spending too much time, we recommend using web scraping tools such as [Browse.ai](#). Once we have collected the charging points, we can use a language model like ChatGPT to standardize the address formats. After normalizing the formats, the next step is to geolocate each address by assigning a point in QGIS. This can be done using the Web Service Geocode plugin. In this way, we will have in a QGIS layer all the points we wish to add to our scenario.

5.7 Adding initial and final points

If we keep the model as it is, some initial and final points of the roads will not appear in the `crossroads` layer. This is because, if they are not located in intersections, those points would not have been generated in the previous procedure.

Although this omission does not prevent the model from running in GAMA, it does affect the accuracy of the simulated road network.

In particular, the absence of these points can lead to an incomplete graph, meaning certain streets do not have correct connections at their endpoints. Consequently, vehicles in the simulation would be unable to reach the end of some streets, affecting mobility and a realistic representation of urban traffic.

To fix this issue, we must extract the vertices corresponding to the road endpoints and manually add them to the `crossroads` layer, thus ensuring a complete and functional road network within the simulation environment.

We address this problem by using the `Extract Specific Vertices` tool, based on the road network. This tool allows us to identify and extract the start and end points of each road segment that were not generated previously.

We will apply this technique to extract the vertices into two separate layers:

- **Initial vertices:** selected using the expression `0`, which will retrieve the start points of each road.
- **Final vertices:** extracted using the expression `-1`, thus identifying the endpoints of each road segment.

Figure 7: A roundabout with various color-coded points according to their layer: purple for intersections, green for endpoints, and orange for starting points.

Once all points have been obtained, it is necessary to select only those not already present in the *crossroads* layer. We will use the **Select by Location** tool, following these steps:

1. **Enable editing mode** in the respective layer.
2. **Select the points:**
 - Extract the initial (0) and final (-1) points.
 - Using the **Select by Location** tool, compare with *crossroads* and select those that intersect, touch, or overlap.
3. **Delete duplicate points** using the **Delete selected features** option.
4. **Assign field values**, labeling the remaining points as "crossroads" in the *highway* field.
5. **Save the layers** with descriptive names such as **InitialVertices** and **FinalVertices**.

This ensures that all intersections and relevant points are correctly included in the graph without redundancies.

Next, merge vector layers, specifically the layer of initial points, final points, and intersections into a single one. Rename them with the field calculator so that the *highway* field has the value 'crossroad'.

5.8 Avoiding duplicate points and prioritizing OSM Data

In some cases, a point from **InitialVertices**, **FinalVertices**, or the intersection set may coincide with a point of information downloaded from OSM—such as a traffic light located at a road intersection, which is quite common.

To avoid duplication and ensure data consistency, we will once again use the **Select by Location** tool, comparing the newly created layer (including all intersections along with the initial and final points) with the OSM downloaded point layer. Matching points must be deleted from the new layer. We could also have used the **Delete Duplicate Geometries** tool for this step.

This allows us to identify matches and give priority to the data in the point-of-interest layer, ensuring that important attributes like traffic lights or other elements are correctly maintained in the graph when we finally merge all point layers.

5.9 Removing false intersections

The new cleaned layer will contain all the road intersections identified on the map. However, it is crucial to differentiate cases where two roads visually appear to intersect but should not actually form a real intersection—for example, bridges and underpasses at different levels.

Even if roads appear to overlap in the map, if they are at different altitudes, they should not be considered intersections.

Figure 8: Representation of a highway with an exit leading to a roundabout located at a higher level. Wrongly generated intersections can be observed at points where the roads do not actually intersect. This highlights the need to clean the road graph by removing false connections.

We remove all vertices corresponding to false intersections from the map. To do this, enable editing mode for the respective layer, select the vertices to be removed (highlighted in orange in the figure above), and use the delete tool (trash icon) to remove them, ensuring an accurate representation of the road network.

5.10 Merging layers and saving nodes.

At this point, we have gathered all the necessary nodes for the simulation, including traffic lights, signals extracted from OSM, initial and final points, road intersections, and other relevant elements, such as charging stations. However, these nodes might be distributed across different layers.

To consolidate them into a single layer, we use the **Merge Vector Layers** tool, selecting all the layers containing the nodes. As a result, we will obtain a unified layer with all the elements needed for our scenario, and there will be no duplicates.

After generating this layer, open the **attribute table** to review and fix any incomplete or incorrect columns, ensuring the information is properly integrated.

Finally, save the layer with a descriptive name, such as *crossroads*, to keep all points organized. To do this, right-click on the layer and select: **Export - Save Features As**.

6 Modify the roads

Having generated the nodes, we now need to adjust the existing roads so that they match up with these points, thus ensuring the consistency of the road graph.

6.1 Install SAGA Next Gen

To modify the roads layer, we will use SAGA GIS, an open-source platform providing a wide range of tools for geospatial data processing and analysis. To leverage its capabilities, it must be installed and configured first.

6.2 Cut roads by points

By analyzing together the nodes and roads of the various layers created so far, it may be observed that some lines overlap certain points without those points necessarily matching the endpoints of those lines.

Since our goal is to build a coherent and functional graph, we must adjust the geometry of the roads to ensure that all connections occur at starting or ending points of the road segments.

Figure 9: A road line overlapping a point of information on the map.

To achieve this, after installing the **SAGA Next Gen** plugin, we use the *Split lines at points* tool. This option divides a line or set of lines at the specified points. In this case, we select the previously created roads layer and use the points from our newly generated road-node layer to perform the split.

Figure 10: A road line overlapping two points of information on the map.

Figure 11: The same road line after using SAGA Next Gen's *Split lines at points*. Notice the difference: where previously there was a single line, now it is divided into three segments that respect the corresponding nodes.

Now, the roads are segmented at key points, such as traffic lights, intersections, crosswalks, and stop signs. It is crucial that these points act as intermediate nodes in the graph, since they enable dynamic management of essential aspects, such as blocking or releasing passage and accurately simulating traffic behavior.

6.3 Solve problems with the length

This process generates lines with zero length, which are irrelevant and can cause problems in the simulation or at least create confusion and consume resources.

To eliminate these elements, we use the **Select by Expression** tool. First, select all roads in the working layer, then access the *Processing* menu and open the **Toolbox**. Inside, choose **Select by Expression** and configure the tool by selecting the input layer and applying the expression ' $\$length = 0$ '. This identifies all lines of zero length, which should be deleted from the layer.

7 Create pedestrian streets

The goal of this section is to create a separate graph for pedestrians, different from the graph that cars will use.

Many sidewalks are not recorded in OpenStreetMap (OSM) or are partially recorded, requiring us to create them manually. However, doing so one by one would be tedious and poorly scalable, so it is necessary to resort to creative and ingenious solutions, such as the one proposed below.

The **Buffer** tool in QGIS allows the generation of buffer zones around spatial features—in other words, creating polygons around lines. In our case, it can be useful to buffer the roads, assuming the sidewalks are represented by lines located along the edges of those roads.

7.1 Create sidewalks with buffers

To create a buffer in QGIS, go to the main menu:

Vector → **Geoprocessing Tools** → **Buffer**

Then select the roads layer. It is crucial to enable the *dissolve* option so that a single polygon is generated rather than multiple independent polygons.

The buffer distance can be set according to the needs of the analysis. A recommended value is 5×10^{-4} degrees for appropriate results at the scale of the study.

Figure 12: Result of creating a buffer around the roads layer in QGIS.

To convert the buffer polygons into lines, you must access the following tool in QGIS:

Geometry Tools → Polygons to Lines

For the **polygon input**, select the previously generated buffer layer. Once this operation is executed, you will obtain a set of lines representing the edges of the buffer. In the case of roads, this implies generating two lines per road, corresponding to the sidewalks on each side. To divide the urban area into city blocks, the *Split with Lines* tool should be used, as it has been previously applied in this project.

7.2 Create crosswalks

By following the steps described in this manual, at this point in the process you should have:

- A node at each crosswalk intersection with the road line, representing the space used by vehicle traffic.
- Lines corresponding to sidewalks, where pedestrians are expected to walk.
- However, the crosswalk lines connecting both sides of the street are not yet joined.

To resolve this problem, the first step is to select only the crosswalks. To do so, follow these steps:

1. Select the **crossroads** layer.
2. Apply a filter using the following procedure:
 - Right-click on the layer → **Filter**.
 - In the pop-up window, filter by expression: "highway" = 'crossing'.
3. To save the selection in a new layer:
 - Right-click on the layer → **Export** → **Save Features As**.

This procedure isolates the crosswalks in a separate layer, making them easier to manipulate.

Next, we enable layer editing with the pencil icon . This tool allows us to align or “snap” the vertices or segments from one vector layer to another.

We then use the add line tool to manually trace the crosswalks. This involves:

1. Drawing a line connecting a sidewalk point to the crosswalk node we filtered earlier.
2. Drawing another line from that crosswalk node to the sidewalk on the opposite side.

Thus, we add the segments needed to complete the sidewalk layer.

This is the least automated process for mapping the city because it involves manually creating the crosswalks. During the project, there has been research aimed at streamlining this task, achieving a certain degree of automation through a script. However, while it handles most crosswalks correctly, this method fails in some points due to data idiosyncrasies, such as double crosswalks or very close ones, which greatly complicate automation.

Another possible avenue of research involves exploring the **SAGA Next Gen - Vector Line Tools - Convert point to line(s)** tool to efficiently convert crosswalk points into lines. Nevertheless, it also does not work in all cases; challenges like overlapping or multiple connections still require more advanced logic for accurate mapping.

Having created the crosswalks, as with the roads, we need to ensure node consistency and that all necessary nodes are present. We use the “Line Intersection” tool as before, so we can identify any newly created points.

Figure 13: Resulting arcs and nodes from this process, where sidewalks are built around the roads.

At this point, we have the newly created nodes, so we could consider the task finished. However, we may find that the crosswalks appear duplicated in the map: there is one node in the **crossroads** layer and another node in the intersection layer. Since, in agent-based simulation, pedestrians and vehicles share the crosswalks as a single thoroughfare element, it is necessary to remove this duplication.

To do this, select all the objects in the intersection layer and use the Select by Location tool. Within that selection, filter specifically for those objects that intersect, touch, or overlap with an object in the **crossroads** layer (which contains the crosswalks). This procedure identifies the duplicated or redundant elements between both layers so that they can be deleted.

Remove the duplicates from the selection. Although we could have one layer for sidewalk nodes and another for road nodes, we will merge them into a single layer. Before proceeding, we recommend assigning the attribute **highway** the value **'street'** to all nodes of the layer, allowing them to be easily distinguished upon merging.

We now go to **Vector general > Delete duplicate geometries**. This removes the duplications generated by the “Line Intersection” algorithm.

7.3 Join road nodes and sidewalks

Once the previous step is completed, we can combine the layers. We use the **Merge Vector Layers** tool to unify both the **crossroads** layer and the cleaned sidewalk intersection layer. This will produce a single layer containing all the nodes, ready for integration into the simulation model.

We can open the attribute table of the combined layer to check that it includes both sidewalk nodes (labeled **Street**) and road nodes (**crossroad**, **traffic**, **stop**, **crossing**, etc.). We can also simplify the table by removing the fields **path** and **layer**, as they are not relevant.

7.4 Make sidewalks bidirectional

Select the street layer, which already includes sidewalks and integrated crosswalks, and use the **Reverse line direction** tool to change the orientation of the lines. Then merge both vector layers (one for each direction) into a single one and export the layer. This ensures that pedestrians can walk on the sidewalks in both directions.

8 Create buildings

8.1 Download buildings in QGIS

To download buildings in QGIS, use the "building" key in the corresponding field within the **Quick-OSM** tool, just as we did earlier for roads.

This way, you will obtain all the buildings in the area of interest. If you need to filter by specific values, you can consult detailed information on the following page:

[Key:building - OpenStreetMap Wiki](#)

Figure 14: QuickOSM menu with the **highway** key entered.

Additionally, we recommend also downloading elements related to the key "leisure," which includes parks and leisure areas such as stadiums. Subsequently, both vector layers can be merged using the **Merge Vector Layers** tool.

Figure 15: An image of the layers corresponding to sidewalks, roads, and buildings.

8.2 Data structure

In the simulation, the values of different fields will be key to distinguishing and categorizing various elements of the environment, such as **workplaces**, **residential areas**, **parks**, and **leisure spaces**.

We recommend using an organized structure that allows a clear classification. One example of such an organization is shown in the figure below:

In this manner, a single file integrates various types of values, combining elements labeled in OpenStreetMap under the "building" key with others classified as "leisure". Additionally, each of these elements contains specific information about its category, allowing us, for example, to differentiate if a building is a **commercial space** or if a leisure area is a **park**.

full_id	osm_id	osm_type	highway	destination
w4088867	4088867	way	living_street	NULL
w4263086	4263086	way	tertiary	NULL
w4328605	4328605	way	residential	NULL
w4328606	4328606	way	residential	NULL
w4328607	4328607	way	residential	NULL
w4328608	4328608	way	residential	NULL
w4328609	4328609	way	residential	NULL
w4328612	4328612	way	living_street	NULL
w4328613	4328613	way	living_street	NULL
0 w4328614	4328614	way	living_street	NULL
1 w4328769	4328769	way	tertiary	NULL
2 w4328770	4328770	way	living_street	NULL
3 w4328771	4328771	way	living_street	NULL
4 w4328775	4328775	way	pedestrian	NULL

Figure 16: Example of an organized structure for categorizing elements in the simulation.

Likewise, the attribute table in **Figure 17** includes three additional attributes related to "railway", corresponding to train stations. If more relevant OSM keys are required, they can be downloaded and added to the same vector layer, following the same procedure.

If there are **duplicate, overlapping, or irrelevant elements for the analysis**, you can remove them simply by enabling editing mode (pencil icon) and deleting them directly from the vector layer.

9 Implementation in GAMA

Once we reach this point, we have created all the elements in the map. Now it is time to test their functionality within the simulation.

To do this, we must configure the corresponding paths to the `.shp` files for the **crossroads**, **roads**, and **building** layers. This configuration will enable us to verify whether data integration has been carried out correctly and if the simulated environment accurately reflects the processed data.

9.1 Import geospatial files

To integrate the data into the simulation, we must import the relevant files for each element of the urban environment. The syntax for importing shapefiles in **GAMA** is as follows:

```
file shapefileRoads <- file("../includes/Mapas/Leganes/ROADS.shp");
file shapefileCrossroads <- file("../includes/Mapas/Leganes/CROSSROADS.shp");
file shapefileStreets <- file("../includes/Mapas/Leganes/STREETS.shp");
file buildingsShapefile <- file("../includes/Mapas/Leganes/BUILDINGS.shp");
file shapefileRailway <- file("../includes/Mapas/Leganes/railway3.shp");
```

These files contain essential information for simulating traffic and mobility in the city. However, for the data to be functional within the model, they must be converted into agents and assigned attributes that the simulation can interpret correctly.

9.2 Create agents from data

Once the files are imported, agents representing the different elements of the environment can be created. Below is an example of how to create road agents (**roads**) from the corresponding file:

```
create roads from: shapefileRoads with: [
  lanes::int(read("lanes")),
  num_lanes::int(read("lanes")),
  maxspeed::int(read("maxspeed")) * 0.277778,
  oneway::string(read("oneway"))
] {
  geometryDisplayForMood3D <- shape + (2.5 * lanes);
}
```

This process converts the data stored in the **shapefile** into agents within the simulator. Note that some attributes require transformations, such as converting maximum speed from kilometers per hour to meters per second.

9.3 Incorporate logic for agents

Some elements need additional logic to assign behaviors during the simulation or simply to represent them graphically. This is the case with the agent representing nodes, created with the shapefile we know in this document as the **crossroads** layer, where there might be traffic lights, **stop** signs, or crosswalks. Depending on their type, these nodes have different graphical representations.

Figure 17: Example of the simulation implemented in GAMA Platform. The lines represent roads, and the nodes represent crosswalks (shared by both the vehicular and pedestrian graphs), yield signs, and stop signs. The rest of the graph's nodes are shown in yellow, though in the future these could be hidden. Rectangular colored agents represent cars, and white dots represent pedestrians.

9.4 Mobility modeling

In our simulation, agents represent various types of entities with specific abilities. Vehicles have the **driving** skill, while pedestrians use the **moving** skill. To properly model their mobility, two different graphs must be generated:

- **Pedestrian graph:** Built from the sidewalks, sidewalk nodes, and crosswalk arcs and nodes.
- **Vehicular graph:** Built from the lines making up the roads, the road nodes, and the crosswalk nodes.

These graphs share some nodes, allowing agents from both graphs to interact with the same node—for example, blocking or unblocking a crosswalk when an agent (pedestrian or car) crosses it.

9.5 Implementation of the graph in GAMA

To build the road and pedestrian networks in **GAMA**, we define a set of nodes and edges with associated weights. The weight of each edge in the road network is calculated by dividing the perimeter of the road by the speed limit for that road, while in the pedestrian network we use only the perimeter of each pedestrian route.

```
map generalSpeedMap <- roads as_map(each::each.shape.perimeter / each.maxspeed);
// General speed map in the road network.

list<crossroads> crossroadsRoadNetwork <- crossroads where !each.isStreet;
// Road network nodes (excluding pedestrian streets).

roadsNetwork <- as_driving_graph(roads, crossroadsRoadNetwork) with_weights
  generalSpeedMap;
// Creation of the road network graph with weights based on speed.

list<crossroads> crossroadsStreets <- crossroads where each.isStreet or each.
  isZebraCrossing;
// Nodes for the pedestrian network, including sidewalks and crosswalks.

map generalWalkerMap <- streets as_map(each::each.shape.perimeter);
// Map of perimeters for pedestrians.

streetsNetwork <- as_driving_graph(streets, crossroadsStreets) with_weights
  generalWalkerMap;
// Creation of the pedestrian network graph with weights based on distance.
```

9.6 Possible problems and verification

If, upon running the simulation, you do not see cars or pedestrians moving, it could mean that the GAMA simulation model is unable to correctly compute the routes of the agents within the graph via the `compute_path` function, preventing agents from finding valid paths to travel. This typically indicates issues in building the network, such as:

- Missing nodes in the network, preventing connections between road segments.
- Duplicated nodes, causing invalid or uncomputable routes.
- Incorrectly defined edge weights, affecting route costs.

To check that the graph is correctly constructed, we recommend visually inspecting the network generated in QGIS and verifying that nodes are properly interconnected.

If everything is working correctly, we will obtain a view similar to Figure 17. In this image, cars appear as colored rectangles moving smoothly throughout the simulation, while pedestrians appear as white points also moving fluidly in the environment.

9.7 Scalability

One of the main challenges in simulation is the scalability of the model, since each node or object imported from QGIS translates into an agent in the system. Therefore, it is crucial to optimize the number of nodes and segments, avoiding unnecessary overloads that might affect model performance.

References

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- [2] OpenStreetMap. (n.d.). *About OpenStreetMap*. Retrieved March 31, 2025, from <https://www.openstreetmap.org/about>
- [3] GAMA Platform. (n.d.). *The GAMA Platform*. Retrieved March 31, 2025, from <https://gama-platform.org/>